

Deployment of LSTMs for Real-Time Hand Gesture Interaction of 3D Virtual Music Instruments with a Leap Motion Sensor

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to explore deep learning architectures for the development of a real-time gesture recognizer for the Leap Motion Sensor that will be able to continuously classify sliding windows into targeted gesture classes related to responsive interactions that are used in controlling the performance with a virtual 3D musical instrument. In terms of responsiveness it is assumed that the gestures can be recognized within a small time interval, while the employed gestures are inspired by interaction with real-world percussive and string instruments. The proposed method uses a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network on top of a feature embedding layer of the raw data sequences as input, to map the input sequence to a vector of fixed dimensionality which is subsequently passed to a dense layer for classification among the targeted gesture classes. The performance evaluation of the proposed system has been carried out on a dataset of hand gestures of 8 classes with 11 participants. We report a recognition rate of 92.62% for a 10-fold cross-validation setup and 85.50% for a cross-participant setup. We also demonstrate that the later recognition rate can be further improved by adapting the trained model with the addition of few user gesture samples in the training set.

1. INTRODUCTION

Along with the modern software and hardware advances in Motion Capture (MoCap) technology, the demand for designing touch-less interfaces shown up, which by its side inspires further research activities related to body and hand gesture recognition. Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) applications that directly utilize gesture recognition systems include sign language recognition, robotics, Virtual Reality (VR), and music among others. This paper focuses on hand gesture recognition and according to the literature, two main gesture types are found: *static* and *dynamic* hand gestures [1]. Static hand gestures refer to the postural information derived from the instantaneous extraction

of hand contours and regions of interest. On the other hand, dynamic hand gesture recognition lies on the temporal evolution of the fingers' joints positions and overall hand movement during a performed motion pattern.

However, dynamic hand gestures are still non-trivial to be robustly recognized by computers due to the complex anatomy of the hand skeleton which provides 27 Degrees Of Freedom (DOFs) in total [2]. Hence, the fingers motion trajectories have a great variety of possible shapes which could be subjected to serious occlusions [3], as well as diverse intraclass and interclass similarities that complicate the recognition process [4]. Furthermore, the musical gestures that are continuously carried out during an instrumental performance, are affected by numerous cognitive mechanisms such as visual, auditory and tactile sensorial cues that should be taken into account when designing gesture-driven virtual music instruments [5].

With the emergence of depth sensors such as the Creative Senz3D¹, Microsoft Kinect² and Leap Motion³, various studies have explored the potential of employing such interfaces for interacting with virtual music instruments [6–8]. However, the interaction frameworks that are usually employed in these gestural applications do not consider the active role of prediction, rather than focusing on reactive mappings [9]. Despite recent advances in the fields of Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), significant work remains to be done for achieving satisfactory recognition performance in expressive and real-time music interaction scenarios [10].

Therefore, this paper focuses on recognizing dynamic hand gestures with the Leap Motion (LM) sensor in the context of musical performance with virtual instruments, which are inspired by real-world instrumental interactions. Recognizing such gestures is challenging since: (a) they convey a great amount of temporal information; (b) the recognition window is very short; (c) there is a lack of physical constraints (e.g. specific tangible instrument body or string positions); and (d) there is great diversity in the way a single gesture is performed by different or even individual users. We consider two families of musical gestures, namely, tapping and plucking for simulating percussive and stringed based instrumental interactions respec-

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¹ <https://us.creative.com/p/web-cameras/creative-senz3d>

² <https://developer.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/kinect>

³ <https://www.leapmotion.com/>

tively. The proposed gesture recognition system receives as input the raw hand skeletal tracking data from a LM sensor which are fed to a deep neural network that performs a classification problem of 8 categories; the core-component of the employed classifier is a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). The highest recognition rate for a 10-fold cross-validation setup is 94,5% and 86,5% for a cross-participant setup (i.e. when the data of a participant at a time are left as test-set); the incorporation of few gesture samples from the test-participant is also studied, examining a scenario where the user fine-tunes the system with his own gestures for improved accuracy. These results concern a window-based accuracy (i.e. the recognition accuracy within a window of LM frames), which can be applied in real-time scenarios of gesture recognition in consecutive windows.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows; in Section 2 we briefly introduce some related research works in the context of dynamic hand gesture recognition and gesture-based interaction with virtual music instruments. Next, Section 3 introduces the research problem that we address along with its application context. In Section 4 we describe the collected dataset and the system architecture of the gesture recognizer, while Section 5 presents the experimental setup, the configurations and the performance of the proposed system. Finally, Section 6 draws the conclusions along with a discussion on future improvements and developments.

2. RELATED WORK

Early contributions on the task of 3D dynamic gesture recognition relied mostly on the extraction of hand features from consecutive RGB image sequences by applying computer vision and image processing techniques [11]. However it is quite difficult to capture the rich spatio-temporal movement relations of dynamic hand gestures with a monocular camera sensor [3]. With the advent of innovative depth sensors such as the Microsoft Kinect and LM sensor, there was an increasing interest by the research community to incorporate depth tracking data streams for estimating real-time hand gestures.

One of the first studies that targets sign language recognition based on tracking data from a LM sensor was developed by Marion et al. [12], where ad-hoc hand features computed from the raw positions and orientations of the fingertips are fed to a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier for estimating the performed letter signs. Furthermore, they examine additional features extracted from a combination of depth data captured from both Kinect and LM sensors, which could increase the overall recognition performance. A similar approach was followed in [13], where LM and Kinect sensors were jointly calibrated by means of combining two classifiers for the different feature streams; a SVM classifier for the LM-based features and a Random Forest for the depth-based features of Kinect.

A music related project that utilizes both LM and Kinect sensors for interacting with a virtual music instrument, called “Intangible Musical Instrument” (IMI) [14], targets piano-like gestures. More specifically, two LM sensors

(i.e. one for each hand) are dedicated to recognize the piano-like gestures which are directly mapped to the inherent dynamics, articulation and duration metaphors of natural music interaction, while a Kinect sensor targets the motion trajectories of the head, arms and vertebral axis, which are indirectly mapped to a granular sound synthesis engine. An attempt to use simple artificial neural networks for real-time recognition of piano-like gestures was introduced in the “Virtual Piano” instrument [15], where finger-based features were firstly computed from raw LM tracking data and then fed to a simple Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) classifier. An interesting study that focuses on out-of-range (not captured entirely by the sensors) and overlapping (with significant occlusion) hand gestures is called “Embodied Sonic Meditation” (ESM) [16], where the authors experiment with K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Binary Decision Tree and SVM classifiers for recognizing 7 ancient Buddhist hand gestures named mudras.

With the breakthrough in deep learning architectures there is a growing trend towards the development of complex models that are able to extract high-level features and predict the spatio-temporal evolution of hand gestures. McCartney et al. [17] proposed a 3D gesture recognition model based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), which can identify 2D projections of the 3D space by combining the output of three different 2-layered CNNs for each individual projection plane (i.e. XY, YZ and XZ). A different CNN-based approach was introduced by Molchanov et al. [4], who utilized depth and intensity channels with 3D CNNs, where each channel was fed to a dedicated network. However, most methods either consider pre-segmented gesture data sequences or treat segmentation and classification as separate problems. For instance, Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) [18] and Hidden Markov Models (HMM) [3, 19] have been used as segmentation methods to determine presumable start and stop points of gestures.

On the other hand, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) are able to address this issue, since they are designed to model the temporal structure within a gesture, as presented in [4], where a deep 3D-CNN was used for spatio-temporal feature extraction, a recurrent layer for global temporal modeling and a softmax layer for predicting class-conditional gesture probabilities. It is only recently that some approaches have experimented with LSTM architectures in the task of dynamic hand gesture recognition. The authors of [20] propose a method where firstly 3D hand descriptors are computed from depth data coming in real-time from a mobile Time-of-Flight sensor, which are then fed to a single-layered deep LSTM network as a classification problem of 4 categories. Likewise, the study described in [21] demonstrates the performance of a LSTM architecture capable of segmenting hand gestures from raw LM hand tracking data, which are then fed into either a CNN or a LSTM based classifier. To the best of our knowledge, up to the current date there is a lack of similar deep learning approaches in the context of musical interaction with gesture-based virtual music instruments.

3. PROBLEM DEFINITION AND APPLICATION CONTEXT

In the scope of the iMuSciCA⁴ project, a STEAM (Science, Technology, Arts and Mathematics) paradigm is developed where students, among other activities, have the chance to employ scientific/engineering principles for constructing virtual musical instruments with which they can interact and play music. Accurate music performance is important for achieving the goal of STEAM education, which is the integration of all elements in an enjoying and meaningful experience for the students. The utilization of proper gestures that are inspired by gestures in real-world instruments is also important for offering a realistic performance experience that is related with physical interactions (e.g. tapping a drum or plucking a string). On the other hand, it is not necessary for someone to develop virtuosity in playing a virtual musical instrument, since they can be custom-modified to produce a wide variety of timbres and specific note sets that sound meaningful and interesting. Along these lines, interaction with virtual instruments could generally (not necessarily in the context of STEAM education) serve as a means of musical expression by individual who do not have conventional musical training.

The study presented in the paper at hand and the methodology presented in Section 4 are parts of ongoing research on a gesture recognition module from Leap Motion data, focused on quick gestures that triggering events during performance with 3D virtual musical instruments; these gestures are inspired by gestures used in physical instruments. The ultimate goal is to enhance user experience in the way they control a virtual musical instrument using hand gestures. Although our goal is to have a generic hand gesture recognition module that is suitable for many 3D virtual instruments, we initially restrict the problem by focusing on the interaction with string and percussive instruments.

Therefore, the hand gesture classes mainly concern plucking a string with one of the fingers or using a tapping gesture on a percussive instrument. We aim to achieve recognition of quick gestures in real-time by running a gesture recognition component on successively overlapping windows that slide on the data stream obtained from the Leap motion sensor. Figure 1 depicts the designed real-time work-flow; the focus in this paper, though, is on the gesture recognition task in a single window of data. To this end, the proposed methodology, the collected data and the presented results concern strategies to train and evaluate a system at the window level that includes a single gesture, while follow-up work will study the effectiveness of the framework in a real-time setting of recognizing continuously gesture sequences.

4. HAND GESTURE DATASET AND GESTURE RECOGNITION SYSTEM

The intended application context requires gestures that have not been used in any work so far, to the best of the authors' knowledge. Additionally, the required gestures are performed without physical constraints and feedback,

⁴<http://www.imuscica.eu/>

Figure 1: Overview of the temporal windowing, where successive overlapping input frame sequences of raw hand tracking data are fed to the recognition system.

i.e., there is no physical mass to communicate haptic information about the momentary evolution of the gesture to the user. Therefore, it is expected that different users will perform a given gesture quite diversely; this fact constitutes necessary to employ gesture recognition methods that are based on machine learning from multiple examples, obtained by multiple users. To this end, multiple instances of gesture data were collected by multiple users, which are used to train and test a deep neural network. The collected data along with the code of the presented implementation are available on-line⁵.

4.1 Dataset description

The classes of targeted hand gestures (focusing on plucking and tapping) are depicted in Figure 2 and described in Table 1; the labels in the aforementioned table correspond to the label annotations in the on-line available dataset. We consider in total eight gesture classes, five related with plucking, two with tapping and one “unknown” which allows the system to have a “not in the targeted gestures” state⁶. In particular, we consider the plucking gesture performed separately by each of the five fingers (Figures 2c-2g), while for the tapping gesture we consider either tapping using an open palm (Figure 2b) or with the extended index finger (Figure 2a). For the “unknown” gesture class participants were instructed to perform random hand movement that was as less related as possible with the other 7 gestures.

Data were collected from 10 participants (5 female and 5 male) using the LM sensor for the eight gesture classes (of the right hand) described above. Gesture recording was lasting 2 seconds with an intermediate break of 3 seconds countdown before recording the next sample. Participants provided from 10 to 15 samples for each gesture.

The sample rate was set to 50 frames per second; however, there are always expected inaccuracies in the actual frame-rate, which can unpredictably vary depending on the CPU power and current CPU processes of the operating system during gesture recording. To compensate for the minor differences in the frame length of each recorded sample, all samples were zero-padded up to a specific number of total frames.

⁵<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1260336>

⁶ In the absence of an “unknown” class, the system would forcefully identify every user action (even if no gesture is performed) as one of the learned gestures.

Figure 2: Illustration of the considered instrumental gesture classes corresponding to the right hand. For each gesture, the temporal evolution of the fingers’ motion trajectories follows the direction of the arrow.

The Leap Motion sensor identifies the hand/s that fall within its capturing range and generates a stream of frames, each including information about the the position and velocities among many other properties of the bones in tracked hand/s. All these values constitute the set of 186 features, called the “raw” set of features, that are used to train the system:

Positions: 3D positions of all finger joints (including a zero-length array for describing the missing metacarpal thumb bone), palm center, wrist and elbow (cardinality: 84).

Velocities: 3D velocity vectors for palm center and finger tips (cardinality: 18).

Directions: 3D vectors of directions for hand and each finger, along with the 3D vector of the palm normal (cardinality 21).

Miscellaneous: This set includes the arm and palm widths, length for each finger, estimated pinch and grab strengths, finger touch distances and touch zones, 3D position of the hand’s sphere radius, stabilized positions for palm and each finger, along with the hand type constant (i.e. left/right) (cardinality: 61).

Except from the “raw” features, the set of 30 handcrafted features described in [13] are also used for comparison:

- 5 values for the cosine of the angle between each fingertip and the plane defined by the palm,
- 5 values for the distances between the each fingertip and the palm center,
- 5 values for the distances of each finger from the plane defined by the palm and

Table 1: Considered gesture classes and their labels.

Gesture Description	Label
Palm tapping	RHPT
Index finger tapping	RHIT
Thumb finger plucking	RHTP
Index finger plucking	RHIP
Middle finger plucking	RHMP
Ring finger plucking	RHRP
Pinky finger plucking	RHPP
Unknown	RHUK

- 15 values for each fingertip 3D positions in the orthonormal axis defined by the hand’s direction and normal vectors.

All the aforementioned features are normalized in the range of $[0, 1]$ for each gesture recording; according to [13] the length of each finger is normalised according to the length of the middle finger, which is considered the largest one.

4.2 Gesture Recognition System

As mentioned above the proposed system focuses on the classification task of a single window of input data that includes one of the eight classes. The proposed methodology at its core employs a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network. Figure 3 shows the architecture of the proposed system for gesture recognition of individual windows as input. The input of this network, $x_t^{(i)}$ ⁷, is

⁷ For the remainder of this paragraph, the subscript (t) refers to the window in a sequence of arrays, while the operators (i.e. multiplication, sum and division) and functions are considered to be performed element-

a window that contains a sequence of 75 frames of either “raw” (as produced by the LM sensor) data (186 dimension) or handcrafted features (30 dimension). This input vectors are then “embedded” into a space of a fixed dimension through, a linear transformation in the “Dense linear” (fully connected) layer as follows:

$$x_t^{(b)} = W_i x_t^{(i)} + b_i, \quad (1)$$

where W_i and b_i ⁸ are the arrays of weights and biases respectively in the bottom “Dense linear” layer. This embedding representation is further encoded using a LSTM network,

$$x_t^{(c)} = \mathcal{F}_{\text{LSTM}}(x_t^{(b)}, \vartheta^{(c)}), \quad (2)$$

where $\vartheta^{(c)}$ are the parameters of the LSTM network – defined as a function $\mathcal{F}_{\text{LSTM}}$ of the architecture; finally, the LSTM output is linearly transformed in a space with dimension equal to the number of gesture classes (top “Dense linear” layer) as

$$x_t^{(l)} = W_o x_t^{(c)} + b_o, \quad (3)$$

where W_o and b_o the weights and biases of the top “Dense linear” layer, the output of which is passed through a softmax function:

$$x_t^{(o)} = \frac{e^{x_t^{(l)}}}{\sum e^{x_t^{(l)}}}, \quad (4)$$

which results to the probabilities of each target class. The denominator in equation 4 represents the sum of all elements in the $e^{x_t^{(l)}}$ (element-wise exponential of $x_t^{(l)}$) array. The recognized gesture class is the one with the highest probability, i.e.

$$c_t^{(o)} = \arg \max\{x_t^{(o)}\}. \quad (5)$$

Equation 5 returns the index of the $x_t^{(o)}$ vector with the maximum value (which is the number of the one-hot encoded assigned class).

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

As mentioned above, we have considered two types for input data; the first by using directly the raw data captured by the LM Sensor and the second by using the handcrafted features described in the previous Section. In the first case, therefore, the dimension of the input vector is 186 and in the later case 30. We consider input vector sequences of fixed length, in our case 75 (after zero padding, as explained earlier).

The specific training parameters that produce the results reported in the experiments include a learning rate of 0.001 using the Adam optimisation algorithm [22] for the minimization of the cross entropy cost function, with L2 regularisation of weights set to 0.015, a dropout rate of 0.5 applied on the LSTM cells and gradient clipping during back

wise.

⁸ For the remainder of this paragraph the subscript or superscript indexes (i) , (b) , (c) , (l) and (o) will be respectively representing the (i)input, (b)ottom dense linear layer, RNN (c)lass output, (l)inearly transformed RNN output and (o)utput of the entire network.

Figure 3: Architecture of the employed neural network.

propagation in the range of $[-1, 1]$. These values for the parameters have been set after running a few experiments on a small subset of samples.

In the experiments we have used two types of evaluation protocols: (i) the classical 10-fold cross validation in which we select 90% of the samples per participant and gesture class for training and the rest 10% as test set and (ii) cross participant validation, meaning that we leave one participant out for testing and include the rest in the training set.

For the feature embedding layer, see Eq. (1), we run experiments with dimensions of 32, 64 and 128 for each type of input feature vectors having set the number of LSTM cells to 128. Figures 4 and 5 show the moving averages of the recognition rates on the test set of participant # 7 for 2000 training steps. It can be seen that in the case of the handcrafted features adding an embedding layer decreases rather than increases the recognition rate. On the other hand, in the case of raw data as input the addition of the embedding layer improves the performance, with the dimension of 32 giving the best results.

Having selected the dimension of the feature embedding layer for each type of input data, i.e. 32 for raw input data and no embedding for the handcrafted features as input, we run experiments for different values on the number of the LSTM cells. Figures 6 and 7 show the moving averages of the recognition rates on the test set of participant # 7 for 2000 training steps. It can be seen that for both types of input data the value of 128 give the best recognition rate. We also run experiments with higher values, however, the recognition rate did not improve but it rather decreases.

In addition, we have experimented with LSTMs of multiple layers and we have also considered BLSTMs. In Figures 8 and 9 we present the moving averages of the recog-

Figure 4: Recognition rates for various values of dimensions of the feature embedding layer when handcrafted features are used as input.

Figure 5: Recognition rates for various values of dimensions of the feature embedding layer when raw data are used as input.

Figure 6: Recognition rates for various values of LSTM outputs for input data the handcrafted features.

Figure 7: Recognition rates for various values of LSTM outputs for input data the raw data.

Figure 8: Recognition rates for various numbers of layers of LSTM having input data the handcrafted features.

Figure 9: Recognition rates for various numbers of layers of LSTM having input data the raw data.

Recognition rates for 2000 training steps using the two types of input data for the fold #2. One can observe that in the case of raw data as input a single layered LSTM gives the best performance, whereas in the case of the handcrafted fea-

tures a 4-layered LSTM gives the best results. In addition, we observe that the recognition rates for the raw data as input is greater than the rates we take for the handcrafted features. At the same time the variability for the handcrafted

features is greater than the corresponding variability for the raw data, which means that the proposed architecture in the case of raw data as input gives more stable results during the training process.

In tables 2 and 3 we present the averaged recognition rates on the testing sets using the two architectures in the cases of having as input handcrafted features and raw data for the two types of evaluation protocols, i.e. 10-fold cross validation and participant cross validation respectively. The averaging has been performed with the respect to the various runs on the test sets as well as with respect to the training steps between 800 and 900 epochs for the raw data and 200 to 300 epochs for the handcrafted features. We use different ranges of training epochs since the two systems converge after a different number of epochs depending on the training parameters. In addition to the averages we also report the respective standard deviations. As mentioned above, the single layered LSTM on the raw data with embedding result in better recognition rates than the 4-layered LSTM on the handcrafted features in both types of evaluation protocols. Furthermore, we observe that the average recognition rate decreases significantly in the cross participant validation, especially in the case of the handcrafted features. This means that the number of users in the training set is not sufficient to produce models that are generalized enough to give a good performance independent of the user.

In order to address this issue under real-world circumstances, a small number of gesture samples could be given by the user to “fine-tune” or re-train the system, including their own gesture input. To this end we consider the experiments in which we added as training set few samples of each gesture class of the participant and observed the im-

Table 2: Recognition rates for various configurations for 10-fold cross validation

Configuration	Average Recognition Rate	Standard Deviation
Handcrafted + no embedding + 4-layered 128 LSTM encoding	90.56 %	2.04%
Raw Data + 32 dense embedding + 128 LSTM encoding	92.62%	1.82%

Table 3: Recognition rates for various configurations for participant cross validation

Configuration	Average Recognition Rate	Standard Deviation
Handcrafted + no embedding + 4-layered 128 LSTM encoding	63.31%	4.21%
Raw Data + 32 dense embedding + 128 LSTM encoding	85.50%	2.36%

Table 4: Recognition rates of subjects with ids #5 and #7 for different number of gesture samples in the training set

Number of samples in training set	Participant #5	Participant #7
0	89.55%	71.03%
2	89.81%	85.38%
5	94.29%	85.81%

provement of the recognition rate. The results presented in Table 4 demonstrate the corresponding average recognition rates for the training steps between 800 and 900 on the test sets of users with ids #5 and #7, following the aforementioned “real-world” scenario where the user would provide a number of training samples. The results in Table 4 indicate that by adding few samples of the user would lead to better accuracy: for user with id #5 average accuracy increases from 89.55% (when no “fine-tuning” gestures are included in the training data) to 94.29% when 5 gestures are given, while for user with id #7 the average accuracy increases from 71.03% up to 85.81%. This shows that a system implementation would benefit from asking the user to provide some “personal” gesture samples.

The experiments run on a computer with Intel Core i7 at 2.80 GHz processor and 16 GB RAM, and for the implementation we used the TensorFlow™ framework. We observed that the average time of the system to produce the class of an input sequence of 75 frames was around 85 msec. This fact provides an indication that this recognition rate could suffice for real-time applications, even though a rigorous evaluation of real-time capabilities of the presented method is left as future work.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, we have showed that a single layer LSTM on an embedding representation of raw data sequences of Leap Motion Sensor can be the basis of a real-time gesture interaction engine for performing with virtual musical instruments. Although we have not yet employed the system to a real-time setting, we have strong indications of its responsiveness and its high precision recognition rate. We have also demonstrated that although the system is not user independent, the recognition rate can be further improved by adding in the training data a few samples of the user gestures. Our future work, will focus on integrating the proposed LSTM network to a system that recognizes sequences of gestures in real time, experiment with other deep architectures, e.g. by considering CNNs, and try to improve the performance by making it more user independent.

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